

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

TEACHING COMPUTER SCIENCE AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY ON THE BASIS OF A DIFFERENTIAL APPROACH

Yallayev Bakhtiyor Salimovich

Student of Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov

Abstract

This article examines the main directions of differentiated education in the lesson of computer science and information technology. The need for a differentiated approach in the lesson of computer science and information technology, as in all subjects, was identified and determined. The organization of teaching in the context of differentiation of lessons is considered.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada informatika va axborot texnologiyalari darsida tabaqalashtirilgan ta'limning asosiy yo'nalishlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Barcha fanlar singari Informatika va axborot texnologiyalari darsida tabaqalashtirilgan yondashuv zarurligi aniqlandi va belgilandi. Darslarni differensiallashtirish sharoitida o'qitishni tashkil etish ko'rib chiqiladi.

Keywords: *education, differentiation, differential, approach, computer science, information technology, standard thinking, creative ability.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ta'lim, tabaqalashtirish, differensial, yondashuv, informatika, axborot texnologiya, standart fikrlash, ijodiy qobiliyat.*

Currently, the differentiation of education is becoming one of the main directions of updating the education system.

The teaching of computer science and information technology as a subject creates particularly great opportunities for the implementation of differentiation, for the following reasons:

- firstly, the potential of information technologies being introduced into the educational process of computer science and information technology;
- secondly, the broad interdisciplinary connections of this subject;
- thirdly, an important practical component of the educational content - information technology tools and methods of their use in various spheres of human activity, which provides a natural field for differentiating the educational content.

The need for a differentiated approach to students arises from the fact that students differ in their abilities, types of memory, level of preparation, perception of the world around them, and character traits. The teacher's task is to provide students with the opportunity to show their individuality, imagination, and creativity, to get rid of a sense of fear, and to instill confidence in their abilities. Differential education allows each student to work at his or her own optimal pace, provides the opportunity to complete the task, increases interest in learning activities, and creates positive learning motivation.

When learning new material, we can create groups of different levels depending on the quality of knowledge:

strong - first group;

average - second group;

weak - third group.

By way of thinking:

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

the first group - students with standard thinking skills;

the second group - students with creative abilities. Students with the same level of preparation, learning speed and motivation feel more comfortable studying in the same group.

The teacher explains the topic to the whole class; if there are no questions from the students of the first group (strong students), they receive creative tasks.

The topic is explained again for the students of the second and third groups. If there are no questions here, the students of the second group receive tasks with elements of creativity.

Students of the third group are again explained the material using tables and textbooks and given practical assignments. The forward movement is based on returning to what has been learned, intensive consolidation on numerous examples and exercises, everyone works according to their capabilities and capabilities, without losing interest in science. If a student of the second and third groups works at full strength and can complete the assignments, he can move on to another group. Everyone gets his fair share.

But dividing students into groups has both positive and negative aspects.

The positive aspects include:

- excluding the equalization of children;
- Easier assimilation of material in weak groups;
- Faster development of strong students in education;
- Increased self-awareness of students;
- Ability to work effectively with “difficult” people;
- Increases the level of motivation of students;
- Training is focused on the “zone of proximal development of the student”;
- Ability to help the “weak”.

Negative aspects:

- Socio-economic inequality is emphasized;
- Separating children according to their level of development is inhumane;
- Transferring to weak groups negatively affects children's self-esteem;
- The level of self-awareness decreases: the illusion of exclusivity appears in elite groups;
- The level of motivation to learn decreases in weak groups;
- The weak are deprived of the opportunity to reach out to the strong, receive help from them, and compete with them;
- Additional effort and time to create and check multi-level tasks;
- Imperfection of diagnostics.

Highly prepared students require special attention. Often, when working as a whole group, they are left with little work. Such students need challenging, non-standard work and creative work tasks, which will allow them to develop their learning abilities to the maximum.

- A strong student can act as a teacher or his assistant. In this case, knowledge is not only polished, but also a deeper understanding is achieved, the ability to apply knowledge in practice is formed, and organizational skills are formed. Assistants can perform the following functions:

- checking the assignments completed by students, reviewing the work;
- helping weak students correct mistakes after tests and independent work;
- performing the duties of consultants during group work, laboratory and practical work;
- summarizing at the end of the lesson.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

Computer science and information technology, like other disciplines, allows you to approach almost any educational task at two levels of complexity: the student performs the required task using information technologies that are familiar to him (or within his capabilities), or the student strictly adheres to the established requirements.

The organization of education in conditions of level differentiation allows:

- to achieve an increase in students' interest in knowledge and cognitive activity;
- to systematize individual work with students;
- to significantly reduce the number of unsuccessful students;
- to increase the quality and strength of knowledge;
- to identify gaps in students' knowledge;
- to create psychological comfort in the lesson for both the student and the teacher.

Any problem, and first of all, in education, cannot be solved without constant adherence to the rule: if there is no mutual understanding, cooperation between adults and children, mutual respect, nothing will work. The upbringing and education of a person is a complex, multifaceted task that is always relevant. Each child has enormous potential, the realization of which largely depends on adults. And the task of the teacher, first of all, is to help the student become free, creative and responsible, capable of self-determination, self-affirmation and self-realization.

References

1. Alekseev, N.A. Psychological and pedagogical problems of developmental and differentiated learning. - Chelyabinsk, 1995. - 174 p.
2. Boronenko, T.A. The concept of a school course in computer science: a teaching aid. - St. Petersburg, 1995. - 68 p.
3. Lapchik, M.P. Methods of teaching computer science: A manual for students of pedagogical universities / M.P. Lapchik, I.G. Semakin, E.K. Henner; Under the general editorship of M.P. Lapchik. - Moscow: Publishing center "Academy", 2001. - 624 p.
4. Osmolovskaya, I.M. Differentiation of learning: pros and cons // School technologies. – 2001. – P.16- 18.
5. Unt I.E. Individualization and differentiation of learning. – M., 1990. – 192s.
6. Yakimanskaya, I.S. Personality-oriented learning in a modern school / I.S. Yakimanskaya. – M., 1996. – 96s.